

THE CONCEPT OF CRIMES OF A TERRORIST NATURE AND THEIR CRIMINAL LAW BASIS

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Abstract: "Terrorism" and "terrorist acts" have become one of the most terrible and dangerous problems facing humanity in the 21st century, manifesting in various forms. "Terrorism" and "terrorist acts" - in all their manifestations, have become actions that have become one of the most terrible and dangerous problems of humanity in the 21st century. These crimes threaten the security not only of individual countries or regions but of all humanity. In recent years, crimes of a terrorist nature have acquired transnational and cross-border characteristics, with their level of social danger sharply increasing. Consequently, there is a growing need to improve criminal law and criminological methods and foundations for combating crimes of a terrorist nature, and their further enhancement in national legislation is crucial.

Keywords: "terror," "terrorism," "terrorist activity," "terrorism-related crimes," and "crimes of a terrorist nature."

The word "terror" is derived from Latin, meaning "fear" or "horror." [1] "Terrorism" is a process of pursuing criminal, political, ideological, and personal goals by intimidating the population and exerting pressure on state authorities and governing bodies.

The word "terrorism" was first introduced during the French Revolution of 1793-1794. At that time, this word was used in a positive sense and was considered an expression of struggle against the oppression of people by rulers when tyranny became excessive.

Terrorism (from Latin terror - fear, terror) - violent actions (harassment, destruction, hostage, murder, detonation, etc.) aimed at eliminating or intimidating political opponents, opponents, causing panic and disorder among the population. Terrorism is divided into individual and group terrorism (e.g., the actions of extremist political gangs). [2],[3]

In political science, the concept of state terrorism is also used (repressions of dictatorships and totalitarian regimes). Terrorism has been occurring in all regions and countries since the Middle Ages. But since the end of the last century, new manifestations of it have emerged (murder or abduction of heads of foreign states and governments, their diplomatic representatives, blasting of embassies, missions, buildings of international organizations, bombings at airports and railway stations, hijacking of aircraft, hostage taking of people, etc.).

International terrorism became widespread, and terrorism began to take on an open political character. There have been cases where terrorists have received support from the governments of some countries and related structures. The level of public danger of crimes committed by them has increased. The threat of nuclear, chemical, and biological weapons falling into the hands of terrorists has increased, and electronic terrorism has emerged. In many cases, terrorism began to be intertwined with religious extremism, drug trafficking, and separatism. Most countries have adopted multilateral conventions and laws to strengthen the

fight against terrorism. Specifically, a special law "On Combating Terrorism" was adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2000. 15 dec.). In this Law, Terrorism is defined as an act of violence, threat of use of force or other crimes provided for by the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, aimed at forcing the state, an international organization, an individual or legal entity to commit or refrain from committing any actions, complicating international relations, violating the sovereignty, territorial integrity, undermining the security of the state, instigating armed conflicts, destabilizing the political situation, threatening the population, threatening the use of force or other crimes, posing a threat to The law legally substantiates issues such as the powers of state bodies in the field of combating terrorism, the conduct of anti-terrorist operations, compensation for damage caused by terrorist acts, and the social rehabilitation of victims.

Although the literature on criminal law does not provide a detailed analysis of crimes of a terrorist nature, the literature uses concepts such as "terrorism," "terrorism," "terrorist activity," "crimes related to terrorism," and "crimes of a terrorist nature."

Based on the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the laws "On Combating Terrorism" and "On Countering the Legalization of Proceeds from Criminal Activities and the Financing of Terrorism" and the definitions given in legal literature, terrorism (derived from the French word "fear," "horror," "disorder," "vibration, trembling") is defined as "complicating international relations, violating the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the state, undermining its security, causing wars and armed

According to Article 7 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the appropriation of powers of state power, suspension or termination of the activities of government bodies, the formation of new and equivalent structures of power in a manner not provided for by the Constitution are unconstitutional and serve as grounds for prosecution under the law.

This liability is provided for in Article 159 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to which an open call for unconstitutional change of the current state system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, seizure of power or removal from power of legally elected or appointed representatives of power or unconstitutional violation of the territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the preparation, storage or distribution of materials of such content for the purpose of distribution, entails criminal liability.

Crimes related to terrorism and crimes of a terrorist nature differ from each other.

Crimes related to terrorism are crimes directly related to the commission of this crime. In particular, failure to report information and facts about prepared or committed terrorist acts (Article 155-1), training, exit or movement for the purpose of carrying out terrorist activities (Article 155-2), and financing terrorism (Article 155-3) are crimes related to terrorism.

Terrorist crimes are crimes that are similar to the crime of terrorism but include violent, intimidating, or violent acts that pose a threat to public safety.[4] They are usually used to achieve political, economic, or ideological goals. The social danger of such crimes manifests itself in the following factors:

Fear and intimidation: Creating an environment of fear that leads to unrest in society.

Damage to life and property: assaulting individuals, public property, or state facilities.

Disruption of social solidarity: Polarization in society, aggravation of interethnic or religious conflicts.

Crimes of a terrorist nature are crimes specified in the disposition of Article 155-1 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and these crimes are considered crimes provided for in Article 11 of the Criminal Code, namely: terrorism (Article 155 of the Criminal Code), training, exit or movement for the purpose of carrying out terrorist activities (Article 155-2 of the Criminal Code), financing of terrorism (Article 155-3), assault on the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 158 of the Criminal Code), encroachment on the constitutional order of

However, the disposition of some articles of the Criminal Code contains elements related to terrorism, and based on this, it is advisable to include them in the list of crimes of a terrorist nature. Examples include the creation, leadership, and participation in religious extremist, separatist, fundamentalist, or other banned organizations provided for in Article 244-2 of the Criminal Code, as well as the distribution or storage of materials promoting terrorist ideas provided for in Article 244-1 of the Criminal Code.

Article 2 of the European Convention on Combating Terrorism, adopted on January 27, 1977, also stipulates that actions not specified in Article 1 of the Convention may be considered terrorism if they can seriously threaten a person's life, health, or freedom, cause damage to property, or pose a general danger to people. This means that the document does not define a specific range of terrorist crimes, allowing states to independently formulate this list.

In conclusion, crimes of a terrorist nature can be defined as criminal actions that undermine state and public security, destabilize the socio-political situation, obstruct the legitimate activities of government representatives, often pose a threat to an undefined group of people, are frequently committed on a mass scale, and create an atmosphere of fear in society. These crimes are characterized by their object (peace and security, public safety, and public order), socially dangerous consequences (inciting war and armed conflicts, destabilizing the socio-political situation, intimidating the population, causing death or bodily harm to state or public figures or government representatives, violating the constitutional order, etc.), and methods of commission (acts of violence, use of force, conspiracy, attacks on life, inflicting bodily harm, mass killings, property damage, etc.).

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